

The Religious Leadership

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ABSTRACT: Religion is by far one of the oldest and most complex systems of leadership. Due to this background, many sociologists asserted that religion is, in fact, the strongest and most useful way of imposing obedience over people without giving something substantial (material) in return¹. Being so controversial and disputed, religious leadership has also several types of getting control over masses, as regarding to the mundane leadership. Mostly these types of control are faith-based grounded and even more, divinely 'giving', as almost all religious leaders claim. Then why these types of religious leadership are so different and fundamentally opposed in most cases, I mean if they are *all* revealed by a divine power? On the other hand, what if these claims are merely a smokescreen behind which leaders to fulfill their own selfish interests? While approaching issues related to different types of religious leadership, its attributes and artificial means of reaching such a position in any religion, I will try to find also answers for the questions above.

KEY WORDS: Prophetism, religiousness, leadership, trust, artificial means, revelation

Introduction

Leadership is most probably one of the religious phenomenon crucial elements, and due to that, I was oscillating between leaving this issue at the end of my work or starting with it. Either way, the exposition can be considered as splitting between two

components, each determining the other's definition by the fact that it stands in front of the other one. That is why I was confident that, leaving RL² at the end, it will bear many features from previous elements, and also these items will not be fully understood unless RL is previously defined and explained. So, here we are, starting with the most common question, *what is a religious leader?*

1. Is it the one who rules a (religious) community;
2. a person who manifests devotion to a deity and proves himself worthy of being a model of that;
3. one who is regarded as an authority on religious law and its interpretation and who has political power as well³
4. those who often give *political*⁴ speeches and criticize "the wrong person," due to their "ignorance or sins,"
5. Alternatively, is it someone who guides or inspires others?

Of course, all these one-sided characterizations can continue forever, but it is not the proper space to do that. After all these definitions, pointing a feature or another of any leadership in general, we can say that the most important aspect of a RL is to *engage* his flock and *lead* it to its purpose/end, whatever it might be—we will see shortly more about that 'given purpose.' On the other hand, how would we like to 'gain' a RL? By self-imposing as one who gives people enough arguments and proofs that they leave the old RL for a new, better-seen and more appropriate one; by larger acceptance as one who is recognized by a religious body as having some authority within that body, or through the means of deception/as one who takes advantage on people's belief/superstitions and makes these tools of governing them? Moreover, what type of RL 'best' matches religion, that who *models the religious views in accordance with his community needs and wishes*, or that who *imposes his religious views to people regardless of their capability of following those rules?*

However, all these aspects are not different from any other type of worldly leadership, meaning that, until now, RL is not different at all from the already known form of human, civil leadership: *management, superintendence, supervision, organization, control, demeanor paradigm et. all*. Still, is there any aspect that makes RL

different from all other mundane leadership or not? This is a great deal to answer to, especially when stating that religion is partially divine while being mostly human.

“A leader is an individual (or, rarely, a set of individuals) who significantly affects the thoughts, feelings, or behaviors of a significant number of individuals,”⁵ . . . whether direct or indirect, leaders fashion stories—principally stories of identity—wherewith he shapes characters, builds personalities, and frames culture. It is important that a leader be a good storyteller but equally crucial that the leader embody that story in his or her life.

Religious leaders who changed the world had an enormous impact on human consciousness and produced substantial changes in the lives of both their followers and to the human society in general. These promoters are known as *religious founders* of some powerful and influential religious current. I.e. Jesus Christ of Nazareth, Mohammed from Mecca, Siddhartha Gautama (Buddha), Krishna, Confucius/Kong Zi, Zarathustra, Moses. Of course, to their number will be added many religious promoters which, although they have given rise to religions other than those already known, *have promoted that belief* by giving it large scale (e.g. Apostle Paul of Tarsus), *have created new trends* (e.g. Martin Luther, Ellen G. White or Carol Parham), *have organized that belief on new principles* and *reinterpreted* the original recipe of their religion through their own experimentation, and therefore giving it a new direction (e.g. Joseph Smith).

Who can provide “religious truths”? Only the religious promoters and religious leaders, or all those involved in the act of faith experiencing fundamental truths in their own lives? The historian of science Donna Haraway’s assertion that “situated knowledges” are more accurate than the “god-trick” of universal or objective claims that rest on the assumption that it is possible to “see everything from nowhere.” Contrary to popular opinion, the recognition that all knowledge claims are “situated” is *not* a manifestation of relativism whereby all interpretations are considered equally valid. Rather, “situated knowledges” offer the firmest ground upon which to make objective claims that are defined not by their detachment but rather by their specificity, transparency and capacity for accountability. The method of “situatedness” assumes that all knowledge claims are

“situated” in that they arise out of particular social/historical contexts and therefore represent particular rather than universally applicable claims. For example, Paul Tillich says what was true for the apostles do not apply for me; the Gospels are very real, a true, historical act, but they are merely the illustration of a personal divine encounter of John’s, Paul’s, or Peter’s and they do not apply to me or you. They are accurate, unambiguous, but there are no less than the personal experience of each of us, and in the historical–social context in which each of us lives, cannot be applicable the experience of the apostles, but the personal one. “But the image is so real and so powerful that it transforms us. Its transforming power points to its historical reality.”⁶

The Limits and Attributions of a Religious Leader

What should a religious leader do and what he should not do? Are there any boundaries when he tries to reconnect his flock with G-d or he just have to do whatever he might consider proper to be done? If he is entrusted with his followers’ life and religious well-being it not right for him to take whatever action he might think it is best for them to do in order to achieve the supreme Good? Alternatively, in other order, it is not just for his followers to take no other action but those their religious leader appointed to, and obey whatever rules he might consider putting over them for the same reason? At the first look, it seems right, at least from the religious leadership point of view. It is said in every religion that the voice of G-d must be obeyed without questioning and contradiction. But at the same time there was always in place a threat in leaders’ minds “What if they won’t believe me and will not obey me but say, ‘The Lord did not appear to you?’” (Exod. 4:1). For that reason any RL came with same result, putting in God’s account his thoughts and suppositions; that way no one would dare to contradict and disobey their will.

Until now we can set these actions as normal attributes of a leader, to settle a pattern of thinking and to try to impose it over his followers. Regarding a RL he is expected to give more than a personal opinion; his followers are always eager to listen to God’s voice through and they never ‘forgive’ a RL that says ‘I do not

know' to a religious question or debate. He is seen as outside the divine call, for he does not have a direct personal connection with deity and thus he cannot speak on G-d's behalf. For that matter we are facing now a boundary conduct born from a demand of the people—"They told me, "*Make a god for us* who will go before us because, as for this fellow Moses who brought us out of the land of Egypt, we don't know what has become of him.'" (Exod 32:23). This demand was always, in time and place, the engine that has started religious movements and has entrusted those who dare taking the role of God's messenger with two characteristics: on the one hand he would have to bestow his life for serving God, so that he must be close to Him at all times. On the contrary he must provide God's will for every lifestyle choice people might ask about, so that he should be available also permanent.

Due to these two needed roles of 'servant of God' and 'religious leadership,' he ends by forcing himself to mastering any situation and to coming up with solutions for every case; he is challenged to express 'what G-d would like' answers every time. With this kind of expectancies no one would end other than expressing their own point of view first, and then, in time, proceeding to overlap it with 'the divine will'. So, for understandable reasons, every RL ends up believing that his opinion/will is, in fact, G-d's and therefore they must be obeyed as G-d would be, absolutely, indisputably.

With this kind of climate around them, RL is definitely constrained to *become* the voice of G-d, and that burden set his mind to operate on a different pattern than all others. He is self-creating a conception of 'elected' and behave in kind, uttering sentences of truth for the people who follow him.

A) What are the Attributions of a Religious Leader?

Well, starting from the evolution of religiosity manifestation it is evident that the primary function of any "leader" is that of the *religious model*, of a pattern, one who leads the way or the promoter of a particular way of meeting the divinity. He is the living "icon" of what the religious conception means; he is the proof that the described/

preached method is real and functional. However, more than a single example, unique and isolated, the religious promoter also has *the declarative function*, of the announcement the religiogen pattern.

To understand the relationship between these two functions of the religious promoter we should see what is the perception their followers have on effect religious precepts have upon their lives and moreover how they do the networking/distinction between the life and the content of preaching. Since in almost all cases the promoter—and not also the subsequent religious leaders—is judged through the predicative content and the beneficial effects that he has had on entire generations of followers, if their lives are higher than average, even of the spiritual peaks. They seem to halt here from the other world, since they know the way and every step towards the pinnacle of spiritual life as if they have went it through, not as they would only have been appointed towards it by a spiritual being. “No one can come to the Father except through the Son . . . that came from the Father” (Ioan 14:6; 16:28). Even where isolated facts appear in some disagreement with the context of his superior spiritual life, they tend to be overlooked or attributed to other functions that we’ll talk later, that of *protection of religious formula*. It could not be otherwise, because any act “not in conformity” with the professed context would harm the doctrinal content. For that matter both the followers and the direct opponents of any religion aim less the religious doctrine and more the promoter’s life. This reality reinforces this first function of the model-leader. The private life of the promoter assimilated with deity spokesman, *prophet par excellence* (another function), is always attacked before the doctrine. This is obvious to everyone by default, that once proved to be suspicious in *n* actions or clearly “immoral”—as nonconforming with the doctrinal message professed—this would discredit the whole serial pattern religious. That is why there was always a struggle outspoken of any religion’s opponents to discredit the promoter’s authority by “discovering” certain obscure acts, hidden from direct followers who feared precisely this “disclosure”. Without saying much or some really remarkable “truths”, lot of underground conspiracy, readings emerged with a clear religious commando tendency. Booklets such as “hidden life of the Prophet,”⁷ “The

Unknown Life of Jesus Christ,”⁸ “The Secret Life of”⁹ are manifestly imposed in a given market to send a clear message to the masses: *just with this unannounced occasion you have the great opportunity to discover what it was hided from you, in fact from the whole religious world until now, and only through these new messengers of “truth” you can find out how and through what tricks you have been deprived of the acknowledgment of the fraudulent deception that you have built an image of a counterfeit religious life.* That is why there was always an outspoken struggle on behalf of the opponents of any religion to discredit its promoter’s authority through these “discovery” of obscure acts, hidden from the followers.

The struggle of religious phenomena for survival was rarely done by convincing the correctness of doctrine or by a test on the prophesied content, but mostly by demonstrating the authenticity of the model offered by the religious promoter. His life reveals that the religious recipe worked starting with him, or, at least on him. Any slippage in the promoter’s life would bring the failure upon the whole system of the professed religious manifestation, even if it would work even better on others. This is the reason why the followers of all great “prophets” and religious promoters have even tried to hide the sides which seemed obscure or even inconsistent with what they wanted to convey through that image; the precursors will always make an iconic “purification” of the image of the archetype for the successors so that they will benefit only from the positive, constructive aspects of the guiding image. Nobody wants to risk “trying” a recipe that has failed the complete transformation to even that one who promoted it; the risk is too great and the stakes too important, this life wasted and the future one lost. Therefore, before joining a new religious system which anyway will never know in all its depths, anyone seeks information on living examples, of people over which the recipe has worked. There are even some confessions, aware of this fact, that maximize their doctrinal preaching impact by encouraging their members to publicly confess “all the good that did their God to them” for having hugged the recipe of that confession. Thus, cults such as the Charismatics and Pentecostal movements¹⁰ have in their proselytism core exactly the method of displaying “the Wonders felt” and experienced by supporters as the

authentication of their spiritual-religious path or even to “produce” (fabric) possible miraculous acts to increase the credibility in their “collaboration” with the spiritual world for those who embrace this path. E.g. Speaking in tongues or “glossolalia” (1 Cor 12:30), Snake handling, Latter rain Movement beginning in the years following World War II,¹¹ and other teachings are not content to merely sit back and be a part of only a spiritual revival, without the power displays of “signs, wonders, and miracles.”¹² But we will come again on miracles when the topic occurs.

In this pattern is framed also the attitude their followers have on subsequent leaders whose life is no longer entirely consistent with the authentic teachings of their religious belief. They tend to sympathize them without accusing of disability the religious recipe they had to transmit. It simply did not work for them and this frames within the error edges that any recipe of this kind has, one that meets a functional pattern with a unique, unrepeatabe person, who’s responsible for his choices and acts. In these situations a later leader’s life noncompliance with the previous examples invalidates him as a leader and not the plan itself as inoperable.

Through the declarative nature of the model it provides the guiding principles for achieving the religious desideratum, the encounter with the divine. This general objective is preceded by a lot of other specific targets generally present in the same form in almost all religions (e.g. mistakes absolution, avoiding disasters, protection against “evil”, improving the quality of life, immortality etc.).

Each of these specific objectives, together with the collateral others, have a different approach and recipe from a leader to another, but they are certainly present in the theological and cultic system of every religious phenomenon. The impulse of declaring its own religious “recipe” are inherently find in each of us, individually, each person being willing to externalize his “discoveries”, findings to others. This function comes to be manifested in two ways: one positive and another negative. First, the proselytism, displays those interested, ignorant, or those previously religiously inactive his “recipe” as the one % sure and as entirely functional pattern. Usually the promotion is done at this stage as compared to other recipes in order to demonstrate the superiority of their own way. Here prevails

the benchmarks, “you have heard that it was said to those of old times . . . *but I say unto you (something else, differently)*” (Matthew 5), which tend to exacerbate valuing this “singular” path. On what this event is based on? Definitely on the safety acquired in repeated experience of the divine presence. This proximity of the spiritual world gives the belief that what he does is perfectly compatible with the divine will and as such, he starts thinking exclusively, meaning that he (the RL) no longer supports an alternative similar in effect, but different in prerequisites (theological, moral, and cultic) so it will always tend towards a unique self-definition.

The conviction of all other patterns come not from an experiment, but from the feeling that if he succeed in ‘touching’ the spiritual world by doing all those things, in this case the recipe is accurate and successful and therefore is must be followed as it is, without any mistakes or deviations. Any deviation from the original pattern is wrong and harmful for anyone who falls from the path. Since there are only few people instructed with recipes of a religious path, it is prohibited to intervene into it by anyone who would rather alter the *truth* and make then a convenient rearrangement of the ‘ingredients’.

And here comes the second manifestation, the negative one, to preserve the original recipe and to guard it against any obstruction by removing any threat, internal or external. This religious leader is willing to make any sacrifice and call any method—even aggressive, violent in most cases—of removal of these threats of corruption of its recipe.

There is of course theological explanation behind this practical, psychological aspect of the prohibition to accept any changes of the original plan. In every religion there is a strong theological foundation emphasizing the need of following a religious path exactly the way it was thought by its promoter. No matter how it is named, they all say same thing that there is one single path since there is a single possible God reveled to the promoter and we all should follow precisely that route. For example, Tawhid (Arabic: توحيد - *tawḥīd*, meaning the oneness [of God]”; also transliterated as Tawheed and Towheed) underlines the declaration of belief in the oneness of God, “an uncompromising monotheism at the heart of the Islamic beliefs (Aqidah).”¹³ This kind of doctrine, found in all major

religious movements, has two-headed aiming: on the one hand, to tell that no other religious way is possible and true, and on the other hand, that the surrender to this path should be total. Confessing that “there is no god but God” allows Muslims to discover that there is nothing real or true in the world but God in his oneness.¹⁴ That utter capitulation requires great effort to maintain everybody—followers or strangers—contained on this path, since it is considered the duty of any RL. In the eyes of any RL, from any religious movement, since the path is God given and must be employed to judge other sources of knowledge, “the greatest sin is *shirk*, “associating” something else (other gods, individual persons, power, money, and so on) with God.”¹⁵ Therefore the aim of this first attribution is “the integration of the whole of life in a unified community,”¹⁶ which grants the followers the intimacy of a personal connection with God the One.

Merging those two functions that features the perpetuation and protection of the religious recipe, its preaching and defense, leads to the *proselytism method*. This is the fundamental technique to any religious phenomenon, one that ensures the achievement of both goals of the leader, it transmits to others the pattern of the possibility of meeting God, and removes all his inappropriate competition that, from his point of view, mislead those who want to reach this climax of spiritual life. Because of the second component the proselytism often dresses negative forms, violent and even terrorist. But this approach is in conflict with the initial religious project and thus it is so frowned upon by some followers or by the local leaders, and disavowed as the official, legal method of the confession, even if, unofficially, it is often supported and encouraged by many followers as another effective technique (through the report impact/time) along with political intervention.

Of course, there are other lots of functions for RL—e.g. the function of transposing and passing his mental image of God’s encounter as a trans-generational transmission;¹⁷ ensuring righteousness by imposing ways of divine intervention and punishment of disobedience; helping people evolve with their spirituality, in the will of becoming a religious advanced person, or in the personal relationship with God, etc.), but this is not enough space and time to develop all those idea.

B) Artificial Means to Become a Religious Leader

Many RL were forced to resort to artificial means to reach this target. Between odd examples I can think of is the use of sex, drugs,¹⁸ alcohol,¹⁹ sleep.²⁰ While in general human society these substances create a state of antisocial behavior, inside religious phenomenon they are used with a specific purpose, that of *Behavioral Disinhibition* (BD), an overarching behavioral trait which is expressed as an inability to resist expressing inappropriate or restricted behavior.²¹ BD is a complex of brain centers inhibition, which are composed of both central nervous system structures and endogenous neurotransmitters communicating between these structures, and it has been termed the “reward pathway”, mixed for their proximity: The core structures of the brain reward pathway is located in the limbic system, including the *hypothalamus*, amygdala, hippocampus, septal nuclei, and anterior cingulate gyrus. Activities that activate this pathway become associated with ‘feeling good.’²² W. Matchett²³ noted repeated hallucinatory experiences as a part of the mourning process in Hopi²⁴ women.²⁵

C. What Makes a Religious Leader be an Authentic Religious Leader?

“Are religious and sacerdotal vocation something internal, i.e., a special grace infused into the soul of the candidate by God; or is the reality involved something external to the candidate, an invitation of legitimate authority to embrace the religious state or sacerdotal office?”²⁶ In most cases of RL—that we will consider talking about few pages later the sacerdotal and individual RL.

After considering all these features of RL we should get back to our question, if *there is any element to distinguish RL from the mundane leaderships?* From our foray in leadership it stands out the fact that RL *ensures* his flock of things impossible to obtain or even prove, but nevertheless believed in. Using this prerogative of ‘being elected’ by god to enact a people of divine interest and pass

on this attribute of election, the RL has the power to overcome any difficulty a person can encounter in life and due to that he give psychological/spiritual comfort, he encourage his flock to move on in great times, to stand still when everybody is staggering (a clatina), to keep on doing things that no one else ('sane') would probably do instead. All these outcomes and many other only a RL can influence his flock to undergo are the result of what a real RL gives to his people; this is not the correct pattern he appoints [since we will see that there is no such thing as 'wrong religious pattern' as opposed to a 'correct' one], the exhaustive explanations about the life he can give, or the unstained conduct he might display. In fact all these features are preceded by the only thing that really matters, *giving hope*. Any religion aims for people salvation; what is this salvation and how it comes to be seen in different religious movements we will see shortly after.

Nothing else counts as much as hope for people; mankind can bargain anything, from food to dignity for the real price, but when it comes to religious belief, he cannot accept any compromise. There are situations in which man fight for wealth, for treasures, for food, water or less, for social/moral/political values or more, but for a proper price he can *be made* to fight or leave fight for any of these motifs. The psychological trigger that can change a fighter into an obedient or vice versa, from a peaceful one into a rampant militant, is giving him hope. How it is possible to achieve 'hope' in such a manner that it transforms definitely and unchangeable a person/group/ entire community? The answer lies not in *the hope* of achieving a higher material state or some goods 'in this life', as other mundane leaders promise for their electorate; in the case of religious promises, the only valuable one that can literally 'move mountains' is that of divine election. Without building a study case of this concept, all religious promoters used it, and with high success I might add.

Knowing the truth is mostly unpleasant and it gets even worse if someone else tells it "in your face". Most often we don't want to know the truth because it will bring down our ego, our will, and eventually our need to live. That is why, paradoxical, people have always come to priests [shamans or whatever they have been called] to find out

the future events of their life and their reason of happening but with a huge doubt that the 'unpleasant' feelings will not happen exactly. For this reason also RL have come with a psychological strategy not to tell the exact and unpleasant truth about the future/present, however instead to bring hope for strengthen the will to overcome these indubitable or revealed events. It is damaging for a couple to be told from the beginning of their marriage, in front of the altar, that most couples [up to 70%] get divorced in the first year, but it would bring hope that whatever misunderstandings they might have—as anyone else—they will overcome with love, care and trust in God's plan that, through the RL, can be made to work out in their favor. That is why RL are not always searched for telling a foretold that is about to happen, but for bringing hope and strengthen the will of defeating that. Therefore, it is not a liar or an impostor that RL who does not 'tell' the future, say a lie or try to avoid a direct and true answer to what future lies ahead. Instead is un-experimented that who does not see the threat in telling people 'the truth', and invent some possible future.

D) Types of Clergy/Religious Leadership

Embedding several attributes and qualifications a RL has to have, we now search for different types of leadership in regard of religiosity (and not of religion alone). In the Western culture, we have four recognized modes of spiritual guidance: *rabbi, priest, therapist, or teacher*. There are also religious leadership that relates mostly to public service and acts of worship, *sacramental clergy* or *universal priesthood*. Each type can be recognizable by a certain qualification or role in which it gives its best yield. Of course, there are lines of engagement that pervade all types of RL in a way or another, but some are higher in a particular type, while other line is higher into another. This is the specialization I will appoint here for each RL type, not as it would make him the unique carrier of that specific quality, but as his distinctive touch.

Regardless of the name each type of RL is called one common requirement is always a rule in place: a suitable candidate to become

a RL must be called by God to have this vocation. “A divine vocation is necessary for the priesthood and religious life.”²⁷ However, how God calls or whom He calls to, what criteria He has to make a divine vocation . . . this is out of our understanding reach. But since a RL is [seen as] more than any laic leader (or a chief, one in charge of something), he is more like a mentor and a coach in spiritual enterprise, that is why increasingly notorious is been used the term “guru” in this regard, even when the concept is not exactly related to the religion in question. Expected to guide and inspire others, the *guru* type is, broadly speaking, needed for more than to rule a religious community. Using his personal engagement and relation with divinity and the world of spirits the guru is what we have called ‘iconic image’.

Guru (Sanskrit: गुरु) is a Sanskrit term that connotes someone who is a “teacher, guide, expert, or master” of certain knowledge or field.²⁸ In the traditions of Hinduism the essence of the guru is especially vivid with regard of the spiritual development, but it also concerns many other sectors of public and private life. With a variety of implications, both social and religious, the guru image lacks of an unified hierarchical organization and strives to play these roles as individual. For the energy and potential spiritual benefits a guru may offer he usually became both means and locus of worship. Traditionally a reverential figure, the guru serves as a “counselor, who helps mold values, shares experiential knowledge as much as literal knowledge, an exemplar in life, an inspirational source and who helps in the spiritual evolution of a student.”²⁹ The concept found in Hinduism, Jainism, Sikhism or Buddhism, has a tradition of inviolability and total entrustment, that is why this figure is even closer to divinity than any other type of RL, and it gets its own place in worshiping. Entrust with more than religious sector of life, the guru is that who reveals the true and whole meaning of life and gives directions to live each and all sectors of life according to the master-plan that fulfills the supreme duty of man. The guru is thus an inspirational source for all human needs and deeds and, “therefore, is of paramount importance in any consideration.”³⁰ In this exhaustive implication of guru in one’s life it must be said that *guru is not a role*, he transcends the role given by his followers or fans and get closer to the heart-function of the guru. It is also stated

that, since the word 'guru' means many things because the guru is a cluster of things, teaches, father-image, counselor, hero, hero, even divinity integrated into one personality.³¹ What is real important for this RL type in spite of others is that, pursuing a path usually strange and hard to digest by everyone else, he impose canons of behavior unto his followers without giving them the 'big picture' but still he never force anyone to do something against their will, because they respect the freedom of the human being. The guru is indispensable for spiritual development, but also remarkable important to any decisions taken in other sectors of life, as one who sees the path and can correct any mistakes during the road. "The guru is indispensable since he is the repository of the people's ultimate knowledge and right action as recorded in the *Vedas*."³²

From these personal involvement and helpful counseling the iconic image of 'guru' passes from the spiritual guidance to almost all type of mentoring (e.g. the "guru" of golf, of marketing, of being a mother, etc.), making an ideal example of a guide out of this term.

SRC—*sacramental religious confessions* or clergy. Unlike the 'guru' figure, where the veneration and entrustment is mostly due to guru's personal charisma and proofs of ascending into nirvana state, SRC personal is mainly needed for religious services and rituals. These aids of acquiring divine attention and support weigh more than the personal engagement, age or experience, since a consecrated person can make at any age a sacramental ceremony and intercede for one's wellness. The role of SRC is closer to rituals and ritualism than to spiritual development, for the outside help more than internal progress.

In this type, there are very few individuals who can rightfully call themselves "Constitutional religious leader." Sure, there are people who know a decent amount of the religious Law, but being an "expert" on a subject is a completely different thing. "The roles and functions of clergy vary in different religious traditions but these usually involve presiding over specific rituals and teaching their religion's doctrines and practices."³³ The foremost aspect of this type is ordaining just few people to do the worship ceremonies and to be the spokesman for either direction: God to men, and men to God. The distinctiveness of the ordained clergy is to perform "rituals

NOTES

¹ One of them, Andrew Werner, says that, while using ‘God’, religion “manipulate and disempower us through fear, imposed ignorance and constant empty promises” through the main construct of religion, ‘sin’, “designed to impose a large amount of guilt onto the whole of humanity”. Andrew Werner, *The horrible truth about Religion*, 2003. See: http://www.bibliotecapleyades.net/biblianazar/esp_biblianazar_18.htm (Last accessed: November 12, 2016).

² This will be a shortage for ‘religious leader’.

³ Cf. <http://www.thefreedictionary.com/religious+leader> (Last accessed: November 12, 2016).

⁴ It doesn’t have to be understood in a narrow terms, as mundane, State leadership or government, but in a larger, wider terms, of engaging both economical, communitarian, law-giving, and others, the ruling dimensions over any type and size of a community in order to make it more efficient and involved.

⁵ Howard Gardner, Emma Laskin and Howard E. Gardner, *Leading Minds: An Anatomy of Leadership*. (New York: Basic Books, 2011), 16.

⁶ Roger E. Olson, *God in Dispute: “Conversations” among Great Christian Thinkers* (Grand Rapids, Michigan: Baker Academic), 239.

⁷ Delbert W. Baker, *The Unknown Prophet*, the Review and Herald Publishing Association, 1987. William C. Henry Sr, *The Unknown Prophet*, AuthorHouse, 2005.

⁸ Nicolas Notovitch, *The Unknown Life of Jesus Christ*, Radford: Wilder Publications, 2008. Robert Sibley, *The Unknown Life of Jesus*, Trafford, 2012.

⁹ Raymond W. Bernard, *The Secret Life of Jesus the Essene*, Pomeroy, 1966. David Aaron, *The Secret Life of God: Discovering the Divine Within You*, London: Shambhala, 2004. Hugo Grotius, Jean Le Clerc, *The truth of the Christian religion*, London: Baynes, 1829.

¹⁰ Gary B. McGee, *Miracles, Missions & American Pentecostalism*, American Society of Missiology Series, no 45, 2010.

¹¹ Thomas D. Ice, „The Latter Rain Revival Movement”, in *DigitalCommons@Liberty*, 2009, paper 48. http://digitalcommons.liberty.edu/pretrib_arch/48 (Last accessed: November 12, 2016).

¹² *Ibid*, 6.

¹³ “Tawhid”, in Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia. Accessed 4.9.2016, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tawhid>. (Last accessed: November 12, 2016).

¹⁴ Juan E. Campo, *Encyclopedia of Islam* (New York: Facts on File, 2009), 665.

¹⁵ Aaron W. Hughes, *Muslim identities: an introduction to Islam* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2013), 82.

¹⁶ Karen Armstrong, *Islam: A Short History* (New York: The Modern Library, 2002), 15.

¹⁷ Vamik Volkan, Killing “in the name of identity: A Study of Bloody Conflicts,” 233. Taking into consideration the permeability of the psychological boarder between the child and the caretaker, the later deposits an adult’s self-image or internalized images of other persons into the developing self of a child (a lasting and very special kind of projective identification).

¹⁸ As the pattern of deviant behavior proves, any substance used in excess or by a deprivation of it would give to the subject the feeling of being elected.

¹⁹ This substance is used in different quantities by lots of people, but with a certain control, it can create a state of unpleasant emotions (sadness, melancholy, anxiety, and frustration) and even limits the consciousness. These experiences are due to the effect of alcohol on the *hippocampus* - a brain area where the processes of brain related to memory take place, and also has suffered from the toxic effects of alcohol itself. Alcohol acts on the *brain reward system* with its euphoric effect (*Neuro-Anatomy and Physiology of the “Brain Reward System” in Substance Abuse*. Cf http://ibgwww.colorado.edu/cadd/a_drug/essays/essay4.htm (Last accessed: November 12, 2016).

²⁰ Deprivation of sleep cases many and odd side-effects, among which would be interesting to mention lower libidos and less interest in sex. It is hence a logical explanation why monks use this technique to overcome carnal desire and get into trance, hearing voices and having spiritual experiences in their brief sleeping time. There are so many cases of people – saints for religious communities – that used deprivation of sleep to achieve religious ecstasy. St. Symeon created a pillar so small in diameter that he could only stand on it. He spent all night on his feet praying, describing the ecstasy of talking to God. Religious persons of all cultures are known not to sleep for weeks during prayer to achieve trances, joy and peace. Cf. Alexander Golbin, M.D., *Sleep Deprivation for Mind Control*. <http://www.sleepandhealth.com/sleep-deprivation-mind-control> (Last accessed: November 12, 2016).

²¹ Cf. to the *Institute for Behavioral Genetics*, University of Colorado Boulder. <http://ibgwww.colorado.edu/cadd/> (Last accessed: November 12, 2016).

²² *Neuroanatomy and Physiology of the “Brain Reward System” in Substance Abuse*. http://ibgwww.colorado.edu/cadd/a_drug/essays/essay4.htm (Last accessed: November 12, 2016).

²³ William Foster Marchett, „Repeated Hallucinatory Experiences as a Part of the Mourning Process among Hopi Indian Women,” *Psychiatry* 35 (1972): 185–94.

²⁴ See Dale C. Allison, Jr., *Resurrecting Jesus: The Earliest Christian Tradition and Its Interpreters*. [https://books.google.ro/books?id=ZbGoAwAAQBAJ&pg=PA274&lp-g=PA274&dq=Matchett+\(1972\)+noted+repeated+hallucinatory+experiences+as+a+part+of+the+mourning+process+in+Hopi+women&source=bl&ots=h-Kzn1eRNiX&sig=wEGf3sfdK8Wa9PpEEYflGR5peT0&hl=ro&sa=X&ved=0ahUKEwjUgPDH1ozMAhUGCywKHejkBY4Q6AEIJTAB#v=onepage&q=Matchett%20\(1972\)%20noted%20repeated%20hallucinatory%20experiences%20as%20a%20part%20of%20the%20mourning%20process%20in%20Hopi%20women&f=false](https://books.google.ro/books?id=ZbGoAwAAQBAJ&pg=PA274&lp-g=PA274&dq=Matchett+(1972)+noted+repeated+hallucinatory+experiences+as+a+part+of+the+mourning+process+in+Hopi+women&source=bl&ots=h-Kzn1eRNiX&sig=wEGf3sfdK8Wa9PpEEYflGR5peT0&hl=ro&sa=X&ved=0ahUKEwjUgPDH1ozMAhUGCywKHejkBY4Q6AEIJTAB#v=onepage&q=Matchett%20(1972)%20noted%20repeated%20hallucinatory%20experiences%20as%20a%20part%20of%20the%20mourning%20process%20in%20Hopi%20women&f=false) (Last accessed: November 12, 2016).

²⁵ John k. Nagel, “Unresolved grief and mourning in Navajo women,” *American Indian and Alaska native mental health research* 2(2): 32–40. [http://www.ucdenver.edu/academics/colleges/PublicHealth/research/centers/CAIANH/journal/Documents/Volume%202/2\(2\)_Nagel_Unresolved_Grief_32-40.pdf](http://www.ucdenver.edu/academics/colleges/PublicHealth/research/centers/CAIANH/journal/Documents/Volume%202/2(2)_Nagel_Unresolved_Grief_32-40.pdf) (Last accessed: November 12, 2016).

²⁶ Edward P. Farrell, “The nature of sacerdotal and religious vocation,” *Proceedings of the Twelfth Annual Convention* (Philadelphia, Pennsylvania: June 24–26, 1957), 171.

²⁷ *Ibid.*, 171–191.

²⁸ Stefan Pertz (2013), *The Guru in Me - Critical Perspectives on Management*, (GRIN: Verlag), 2–3.

²⁹ Joel Mlecko “The Guru in Hindu Tradition,” *Numen*, Volume 29, Fasc. 1 (1982): 33–61.

³⁰ *Ibid.*, 33.

³¹ *Ibid.*, 34.

³² *Ibid.*

³³ “Clergy” in *Wikipedia*, (Last accessed: September 13, 2016).

³⁴ *Ibid.*

³⁵ “There is no other, there is no one like the Lord our God” (Gen 41:39; Exo 8:10; Deut 4:35; 1 Sam 2:2, et.al).

³⁶ “We know that an idol is nothing in the world and that there is no other God save one.” 1 Cor 8:4. “There is no one who does what is right” for “Jesus answered him ‘I am the way [to God], and the truth [to believe], and the life [to live]. No one can go to the Father, except through [believing in] me’” (Rom 3:12; John 14:6).

³⁷ Reza Aslan, *No god but God: The Origins, Evolution, and Future of Islam*, New York: Random House, 2005.